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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.1889101034>

THE IMAGE OF MUHAMMAD FUZULI IN AZERBAIJANI SCULPTURE

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WIZERUNEK MUHAMMADA FUZULIEGO W RZEźBIE AZERSKIEJ

Abstract.

The article examines the formation and development of the image of the classical Azerbaijani poet Muhammad Fuzuli in Azerbaijani sculpture. Beginning with the earliest plastic interpretations of the poet's figure, the study analyses his artistic and aesthetic representation in monumental sculpture. Particular attention is devoted to the first sculptural depiction created by Fuad Abdurrahmanov, as well as to the monumental statue erected in Baku by Tokay Mammadov and Omar Eldarov, focusing on its compositional structure, plastic expression, and its integration into the urban architectural environment. The article also explores the unity of sculpture and architecture, the revelation of the psychological character of the image, the use of light and shadow, and the emotional impact achieved through plastic form. Furthermore, the relief compositions on the pedestal inspired by Fuzuli's poem "Leyli and Majnun" are analysed. The study concludes that the sculptural image of Fuzuli in Azerbaijani art embodies a synthesis of national spirit, monumentality, and poetic plasticity.

Streszczenie.

Artykuł analizuje kształtowanie się i rozwój wizerunku klasycznego poety azerskiego Muhammada Fuzuliego w rzeźbie azerskiej. Począwszy od pierwszych plastycznych interpretacji jego postaci, omówiono artystyczno-estetyczne ujęcie poety w rzeźbie monumentalnej. Szczególną uwagę poświęcono pierwszemu przedstawieniu rzeźbiarskiemu autorstwa Fuada Abdurrahmanowa oraz monumentalnemu pomnikowi wzniesionemu w Baku przez Tokaya Mammadova i Omara Eldarova, analizując jego kompozycję, wyraz plastyczny oraz powiązanie z przestrzenią urbanistyczno-architektoniczną. W artykule poruszono również zagadnienie jedności rzeźby i architektury, ukazania psychologicznego charakteru postaci, wykorzystania światłocienia oraz emocjonalnego oddziaływania formy plastycznej. Ponadto przeanalizowano reliefy na postumencie inspirowane poematem "Leyli i Madżnun". W rezultacie wykazano, że wizerunek Fuzuliego w rzeźbie azerskiej stanowi syntezę ducha narodowego, monumentalności oraz poetyckiej plastyki.

Keywords: Muhammad Fuzuli, sculpture, monumental art, plastic form, portrait-image, urban environment, Leyli and Majnun.

Słowa kluczowe: Muhammad Fuzuli, rzeźba, sztuka monumentalna, forma plastyczna, portret-wizerunek, przestrzeń miejska, Leyli i Madżnun.

The image of the classical Azerbaijani poet Muhammad Fuzuli has been represented in various genres of Azerbaijani visual art. From medieval miniature painters to prominent masters of contemporary fine arts, many artists have repeatedly turned to Fuzuli's poetry, drawing inspiration for their new works from the inexhaustible treasury of the immortal poet's verses.

The question of how Fuzuli's sculpture should be created has always been a subject of considerable debate. At that time, the now widely recognized image of Fuzuli did not yet exist. Creating a stone portrait of the great Eastern thinker was a highly demanding task, and no artist was initially able to accomplish it fully. However, Fuad Abdurrahmanov, a devoted admirer of Eastern philosophy and classical literature, became the first to succeed, producing the earliest sculptural representation of Fuzuli in the history of Azerbaijani sculpture. There are several intriguing hypotheses regarding the creation of this statue - more precisely, about how the radiant image of an elderly man, which appears to us as the embodiment of wisdom, came into being.

It is known that the sculptor Fuad Abdurrahmanov experienced considerable difficulty in creating the image of Fuzuli, which led to delays in his work. Although numerous portrait proposals were presented to him, the artist was unable to perceive the Fuzuli he envisioned. This caused him deep disappointment.

However, one night, suddenly awakening from sleep, the sculptor modeled a figure using plasticine that he habitually kept on a nearby table. According to an evocative account, in his dream an elderly man approached him and said, "I am the person you are looking for."

Only after this experience was the sculptor able to complete what was regarded as the authentic image of Fuzuli. Today, that statue stands as the first among the six sculptural figures adorning the façade of the Nizami Ganjavi Museum of Literature.

In 1958, a competition was announced for the monument to Muhammad Fuzuli to be erected in Baku. A genuine creative rivalry began among Azerbaijani sculptors. The joint project by the talented sculptors Tokay Mammadov and Omar Eldarov was awarded

first prize, and in June 1962 the monumental statue of Fuzuli was unveiled in the center of Baku, in the square bearing the poet's name, in front of the building of the National Drama Theatre (architect G. Alizadeh).

The second prize in the competition was awarded to Jalal Garyagdi and Eljan Shamilov. The authors themselves do not separate their individual contributions to the realization of the monument and regard it as a shared artistic achievement.

The architectural layout of the square where the statue is installed, including its small architectural forms and green spaces, harmonizes with the grey granite pedestal of the monument. In terms of its scale and artistic-aesthetic concept, the sculpture is well integrated into the square and has become an inseparable element of this part of the city. It should be noted that the square was established on the site of the former Quba Square, where old and historic buildings once stood. Today, it is considered one of the most beautiful architectural ensembles in Baku.

Doctor of Art Studies, Professor J. Novruzova notes that "young sculptors immerse themselves in the image for a long time, striving to understand its essence and the possible plastic solution of the monument. Their creative search is directed not only toward revealing the psychological character of the image but also toward a meaningful exploration of the silhouette."

Although the memory of the poet is dear to everyone, and each person may imagine Fuzuli in their own way, it has always been a shared aspiration to witness a convincing visual representation of the great poet, to see the general features and overall appearance of his face as he might have looked in life. From this perspective, sculptors worked for a long time to create a credible image of Fuzuli.

The strength and expressive power of the monument lie in the fullness of its emotional impact, achieved through a multifaceted plastic solution. By prioritizing the richness of modeling that conveys subtle nuances of human character, the sculptors succeeded in creating an image distinguished by expressive modeling, emotional depth, tension, and distinctive individuality. Their profound study of Fuzuli's creative legacy and their ability to identify the most characteristic features of his poetry are reflected in the successful artistic solutions that ensured the fullness and integrity of the poet's image.

Monumental sculpture is closely connected with urban planning issues. The installation of a monument must be organically integrated into the architectural ensemble of a given space, enhancing the beauty of the surrounding environment and making it more visually harmonious. From this arises the enduring question of the unity between sculpture and architecture, as the mutual complementarity and enrichment of these two arts constitute an essential artistic principle.

The sculptors successfully accomplished this task. The features of the poet's face, the subtle wrinkles on his forehead and between his eyebrows, convey a moment of intense reflection and emotional tension. His deeply expressive eyes, mirrors of the soul, indicate that he is immersed in profound thought. The sculptors have depicted the poet in a state of creative inspiration.

The skillful use of light and shadow contrasts on the face enhances the expressive quality of the image. The flowing lyrical lines of the facial features create a moving and contemplative atmosphere. The plastic beauty achieved through refined artistic means is present throughout all parts of the monument.

The total height of the Fuzuli monument is 12 meters. The 6-meter bronze statue, mounted on a 6-meter grey granite pedestal, possesses harmonious proportions, well-balanced dimensions, dynamic plastic forms, and an expressive silhouette. The sculpture is designed to be viewed from multiple vantage points, each allowing the viewer to perceive the richness of the poet's image. As one moves around the monument, different perspectives gradually unfold, enabling a fuller appreciation of the emotional depth of the image and the richness of its plastic form.

The sculptors depicted the poet with his head slightly bowed, immersed in contemplation and silence. Resting his right hand on his chin and holding his renowned "Divan" in his left hand, the master appears to be engaged in an inner dialogue, as if transcending physical existence and entering eternity. By rendering the ancient garment with large, strongly modeled folds, the sculptors achieved artistic generalization and genuine monumentality. They succeeded in creating harmony, fluidity, and conciseness in the lines of the silhouette. Thus, the clear and balanced compositional structure, together with the expressive yet calm silhouette, undeniably contributes to the monument's monumental character.

The stable and refined composition of the monument is distinguished by the seriousness and thoughtful plastic articulation of form. Everything is interconnected; each detail complements the others as part of an integral whole. The dignified and solemn image of the poet, embodied in a figure filled with profound vitality, forms an inseparable unity with the pedestal. This unity is achieved through the carefully considered proportions, contours, and the harmonious relationship between sculptural and architectural dimensions. Moreover, the sculpture, above all, conveys the spiritual qualities and psychological expression of the figure, embodying, in the truest sense, a national spirit. In this image, we perceive the artistic embodiment of the inner world of a true people poet.

The sculptors skillfully utilized the properties of the materials employed in the monument, particularly the bronze of the statue and the granite of the pedestal, whose unpolished lower section creates a distinctive textural contrast.

Fuzuli's lyrical heroes are tragic figures who sacrifice everything in the name of love, regarding it as the highest and purest blessing. This characteristic quality of Fuzuli's creativity is vividly and meaningfully reflected in the bas-relief carved on the pedestal of the monument. The content of this relief is derived from the poem "Leyli and Majnun".

Working in collaboration with the architect Hajibaba Mukhtarov, the sculptors achieved a highly compelling artistic solution for the pedestal. In terms of scale, the successful proportional relationship between the base and the statue lends compositional unity to the

monument. The compositional design of the pedestal itself represents an original artistic achievement of the sculptors, enhancing the monument's overall expressive power.

Although the bas-relief figures are primarily intended to be viewed from the front, as one moves around the sculpture, the side sections of the pedestal reveal subtle nuances and refined details, offering alternative readings and evoking profound aesthetic impressions.

On the pedestal, the sculptors have also rendered the beautiful image of Leyli in plastic form. The plastic treatment of the figure and the face is characterized by smooth, flowing transitions. The refined facial features, the soft modeling of the shoulders and hands, and the profound spiritual elevation conveyed through strong plastic expression transform Leyli into one of the most poetic images in Azerbaijani sculpture. The downward gesture of her helpless left hand and the right hand gently supporting her head are filled with sorrow. The veil thrown over her head falls in soft folds onto her shoulders, enhancing the plastic appeal of the figure. In the expression of the young woman, who seems disillusioned with life, one senses anger and resentment toward her time.

Contrasted with the delicacy of Leyli's image stands the figure of Majnun, filled with latent dramatic tension. Majnun's calmness is only external; inwardly, he is deeply distressed. The intense sorrow that envelops him is directly reflected in his face. He is depicted with his left hand drawn behind his head and his head bowed in despair. This gesture simultaneously conveys both strength and weakness, as though a restrained force is unable to find release from its condition. Majnun's inner turmoil is evident in the tilt of his head and the sadness in his expression. A sense of hidden anxiety permeates the figure, further intensified by the depiction of the lion at his feet.

It is well known that Majnun, having turned away from his time and from society, chose to retreat into the desert and live among animals. From this perspective, the sculptor considered it appropriate to depict a lion beneath the helpless Majnun's feet.

The grace of the female figure, enriched with latent strength, and the contrast of tense masculine force are intensified by the untreated portions of the marble rock, whose rough and uneven surface further accentuates a sense of inner anxiety and dramatic tension.

Through the images of Leyli and Majnun, the sculptors artistically embodied the love celebrated by Fuzuli, love as a luminous and hope-filled human emotion, profound in its depth and intensity. Prof. Jamila Novruzova notes that the bas-reliefs on the pedestal depicting the figures of "Leyli and Majnun" are rendered with such vividness and plastic expressiveness that, even independently, they may be regarded as among the finest works of Azerbaijani sculpture.

The statue of Muhammad Fuzuli, regarded as the result of the joint creative effort of Tokay Mammadov and Omar Eldarov, is truly distinguished by its unique artistic qualities. Within the Azerbaijani school of sculpture, many sculptors have depicted the image of

Fuzuli at different times. However, each of these interpretations possesses its own inner emotional character and distinctive artistic features.

It is also possible to observe conceptual connections between the statue of "Nizami Ganjavi" created by the eminent sculptor Fuad Abdurrahmanov and his sculpture of "Muhammad Fuzuli." Both figures are classical poets of Azerbaijan, and Fuzuli developed his poetic creativity drawing inspiration from Nizami's literary heritage. The statue of Nizami, like that of Fuzuli, is fully harmonized with its spatial environment. The monument preserves its visual integrity and dignity within the architectural setting that surrounds it.

Through an in-depth study of Muhammad Fuzuli's legacy and a thorough understanding of the characteristic features of the great poet's poetry, the sculptors succeeded in creating a portrait-image by penetrating the monument's emotional fullness and plastic character. The skillful use of light and shadow contrasts on the face of the sculptural image enhances its expressiveness. The lyrical features of the face and its soft tonal transitions create a flowing and aesthetically pleasing atmosphere. The plastic beauty achieved through refined artistic means extends to all parts of the monument.

The Fuzuli monument plays a central role within the architectural ensemble of the square that surrounds it, enriching the space and bringing aesthetic harmony to the environment. The work has been duly appreciated by the public. In 1963, the authors were awarded the Silver Medal of the Academy of Arts of the USSR for this monument.

Among the sculptures dedicated to Fuzuli, the marble composition created in 1958 by the sculptor Eljan Shamilov stands out as a successful work. Depicting the poet seated and immersed in deep contemplation, this piece, executed in an outwardly naturalistic and realistic style, adorns the Fuzuli Hall of the Nizami Azerbaijani Literature Museum.

These qualities are also evident in the bust of Fuzuli created by the sculptor Nijat Mammadov. Preserved in the Azerbaijan National Museum of Art, this portrait is distinguished by its profound psychological expressiveness.

A monument erected in the city of Fuzuli, which bears the great poet's name, was created by the eminent sculptor Jalal Garyagdi.

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